

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL INTERPRETATION OF TERMINOLOGICAL PROBLEMS IN MODERN SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT: When we look at the history of translation studies, in the scientific work that has taken place from past centuries to the present, experts have thought about the lexical, grammatical, stylistic, and many other pressing problems of experience. The main purpose of studying the terms is to replace and translate words from foreign languages into words that correspond exactly to our native language. : It is important to translate into Uzbek the terms of foreign languages related to the political sphere of international relations and to find alternative versions of the terms that have been mastered in the Uzbek language and Terminology is inextricably linked with specialist knowledge and hence with special languages or languages for special purposes

Key words: lexical, grammatical, stylistic problems, spheres of linguistics, language culture, linguocultural studies, linguocognitology, terminological systems.

INTRODUCTION:

It is important to translate into Uzbek the terms of foreign languages related to the political sphere of international relations and to find alternative versions of the terms that have been mastered in the Uzbek language in order to overcome the problems encountered in the translation process. Many political terms have entered Uzbek from Russian, and Russian from Latin, Greek, English, French, and several other languages. The study of such terms is one of the most important issues in linguistics. In all spheres of our linguistics, bold steps are being taken to study theoretical issues more deeply and deeply, and a number of practical works are taking place. The publication of different types, i.e. monolingual, bilingual or more, general philological or terminological

dictionaries, can also vividly demonstrate the achievements of our linguists. Linguistics is at the forefront of learning about other languages and their terms in international relations, and their place in language culture. Through linguistics, we gain an understanding of the structure, semantics, cognitive, and conceptual analysis of English, Russian, and Uzbek terms.

Before addressing the main terminological, theoretical and methodological issues, it may be useful to identify claims, assumptions and motivations regarding indirect translation. It is said to be a common practice. Given an apparently still predominant demand for closeness to the source text (ST), ITr tends to be negatively evaluated because it arguably increases the distance to the ultimate ST and, therefore, is often hidden or camouflaged. If translation is deemed bad, because derivative, ITr is worse. It is said to be more frequent in the reception of (geographically, culturally and linguistically) distant literary systems (but see e.g. Maia [2010](#), for counter examples), decreasing as relations become closer. It is also claimed that is followed by direct translation, whenever retranslation occurs (but ample proof against this also abounds). Historically, it appears to decrease when adequacy or source-orientedness prevails, but increase when acceptability or target-orientedness prevails (Boulogne [2009](#); Ringmar [2007](#); Toury [2012](#)). Due to globalization, apparently increases, given that within an international network of power relations, intercultural text transfer is often mediated by dominant systems. As a consequence, tends to be done from one peripheral language into another via a central or hypercentral language within the world system or the regional system of translation.

H. Bektemirov and E. Begmatov write in their book "Periods of Independence": "It is a mistake to think that it is possible to enter any word into the language, to exclude any word at any time. Knowing the place, norms, and extent of interference in language life and speech practice, and acting on that basis, is the best way to regulate and improve scientific terminology".

The current level and scientific value of the Uzbek language in the field of terminology is directly related to the work of Russian and other peoples' terminologists. In this regard, the work of dozens of terminologists, such as N.A.Baskakov, L.A.Bulakhovsky, G.O.Vinokur, V.V.Vinogradov,

A.A.Reformatsky, D.S.Lotte, S.A.Chapligina, T.L.Kandelaki, V.P.Danilenko, made a significant contribution to the formation of Uzbek terminology[14]. The works of Turkic linguists, including M.Sh. Gasimov, B.U. Oruzbaeva, R.A. Urekenova, F.S. Faseev, also made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek terminology.

In addition, the word "structured" needs some explanation: it should be noted that, in practice, terminological collections may well contain not only well structured standardised terms and concepts, but also innovative, vague and unstructured conceptual and linguistic information.

This basic definition of terminology is supplemented in this Final Report by two other terms: terminology work - i.e. the work performed in the creation or documentation of terminological resources » and 13

terminological activities - a broader term which includes not only terminology work but also such areas as training, tool development, and organisational and administrative measures. »

While lexicology is the study of words in general, terminology is the study of special-language words or terms associated with particular areas of specialist knowledge. Neither lexicology nor terminology is directly concerned with any particular application.

Lexicography, however, is the process of making dictionaries, most commonly of general-language words, but occasionally of special-language words (i.e. terms).

Most general-purpose dictionaries also contain a number of specialist terms, often embedded within entries together with general-language words.

Terminography (or often misleadingly "terminology"), on the other hand, is concerned exclusively with compiling collections of the vocabulary of special languages. The outputs of this work may be known by a number of different names - often used inconsistently - including "terminology", "specialised vocabulary", "glossary", and so on.

The work and objectives of lexicographers and terminographers are in many ways complementary, but there are a number of important differences, which need to be noted. A large majority of documents today are designed for specialist communication (including business and commercial texts). They are thus written in specialist language, 30-80% of which (depending on the particular domain and type of text in question) is composed of terminology.

In other words, terminology (which as we have seen may also include nonlinguistic items such as formulae, codes, symbols and graphics) is the main vehicle by which facts, opinions and other "higher" units of knowledge are represented and conveyed.

Sound terminology work reduces ambiguity and increases clarity - in other words, the quality of specialist communication depends to a large extent on the quality of the terminology employed, and terminology can thus be a safety factor, a quality factor and a productivity factor in its own right.

The communication of specialist knowledge and information, whether monolingual or multilingual, is thus irretrievably bound up with the creation and dissemination of terminological resources and with terminology management in the widest sense of the word.

This process is not restricted to science and engineering, but is also vital to law, public administration, and health care, to quote just three examples. In addition, terminology plays a key role in the production and dissemination of documents, and in workflow.

Terminology as an academic discipline offers concepts and methodologies for high-quality, effective knowledge representation and transfer. These methodologies can be used both by language specialists and by domain specialists after appropriate training. In addition, they form the basis for an increasing number of tools for the identification, extraction, ordering, transfer, storage and maintenance of terminological resources and other types of knowledge.

In general, Terminological resources are also valuable in many other ways: as collections of names or other representations, as the object of standardisation and harmonisation activities, and

as the input (or output) of a wide range of applications and disciplines, whether human or machine-based (see the Figure below). The range of applications to which terminology is of direct relevance was a primary motivating factor at the inception of the POINTER Project with its brief to analyse the situation of terminology in Europe, and to make concrete suggestions for a future infrastructure and activities terminological systems, unlike other language systems, occur in the process of classifying, systematizing, and defining scientific concepts. The systematic nature of terminology cannot be justified without going beyond language. The structure of terminology is primarily due to the fact that scientific knowledge itself is systematic and hierarchically structured. Based on the above, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "terminology" and "terminal system"[3]. Indeed, it would be useful for experts and terminologists to work together on terms to ensure that the terms being modified or replaced are simple, concise and, most importantly, understandable to the public[11]. Preserving the linguistic riches of the native language, which embodies the centuries-old experience of each nation, their scientific analysis and transmission to future generations, is one of the most important tasks facing modern science, especially linguistics. From this point of view, as the first President I.A.Karimov said, the study of words and phrases, terms and lexical riches in the "Uzbek language as a means of expressing the national culture and identity of the people" and the linguistic heritage conducting scientific analysis is one of the most pressing issues today.

Terminology is a discipline that studies, among other things, the development of such terms and their interrelationships within a specialized domain. Terminology differs from lexicography, as it involves the study of concepts, conceptual systems and their labels (terms), whereas lexicography studies words and their meanings. In fact, terminology is a many-faceted subject being, depending on the perspective from which it is approached and the affiliations of the person discussing it. Three major points need to be made here: Firstly, proper terminology is concerned with the relationship between concepts, and between them and their designations, rather than with 80 designations alone or with the objects they represent. This point is essential if quality is to be achieved, especially with synonyms and in multilingual environments. Secondly, a

designation does not necessarily have to be a word or phrase, although it often is. Thus terminological resources may comprise symbols, drawings, formulae, codes, etc. as well as, or even instead of, words. This point is especially important given the move to multimedia systems. Thirdly, terminology is inextricably linked with specialist knowledge and hence with special languages or languages for special purposes (LSPs).

As you know, the most relevant, very complex field of linguistics, both theoretical and practical, is terminology. Many terminological dictionaries of the Uzbek language were compiled and published in the 1930s. First of all, in the process, theoretical issues on the history of terms, meaning and subject groups of terms, grammatical structure and construction, the path of development and sources of enrichment were also developed.

This article describes the image of imaginary diseases in the stories of Edgar Allan Poe and the reasons for writing about diseases. The allegory and symbolism by depicting the Red Death.¹

The article is devoted to the analysis of the *The Magic Hat* book, written by popular Uzbek writer Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboyev, from the position of classification elements introduced by my famous Russian philosopher, literary critic and scholar Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin.²

The depiction of natural landscapes given in works of art is one of the factors that demonstrate the creative artistic skill.³

В современной методике так же, как и много лет назад, актуальной и нерешенной до сих пор остается проблема поиска и выбора наиболее эффективных и рациональных

¹ Akhmedovna, B. M., & Shakhnoza, B. (2022). The Image of Disease in Edgar Allan Poe's "The Masque of the Red Death". *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 19-22.

² Kadirova, N. A. (2020). ANALYSIS OF TRANSFORMATION MOTIFS IN THE MAGIC HAT BOOK BY KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOYEV, THROUGH THE PRISM OF MIKHAIL BAKHTIN'S THEORIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 405-408.

³ Kabilova, F., & Tokhirovna, T. K. English Translation of Abdullah Qadiri's Novel "Days Gone by" and Its Reflection Skills. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(10), 304-306.

методов преподавания иностранных языков, соответствующих современным условиям обучения и отвечающих требованиям стандартов современного образования.⁴

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory.⁵

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.⁶

This lesson plan format moves from teachers to centered student. In order to keep this standard lesson plan format from becoming monotonous, it is seminal to memorize that there are a number of variations that can be applied within the various segments of the lesson plan format.⁷

This article deals with the analysis of pastiche in literature, particularly in “The Lightning Thief” by American author Rick Riordan. The research identifies pastiche as a term, which is applied to a literary work that is a broad mixture of things-such as themes, concepts, and characters-imitated from different literary works.⁸

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham’s short story “The Book Bag”. It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁹

⁴ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

⁵ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

⁶ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

⁷ Nodirovna, N. N., & Temirovna, P. M. (2022). Principles of designing lesson plans for teaching ESL or EFL. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 5, 10-12.

⁸ Khabibullaeva, R. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PASTICHE IN THE NOVEL “THE LIGHTNING THIEF” BY RICK RIORDAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 958-961.

⁹ Куницька, І. (2014). Роман-біографія як жанровий різновид модерністського роману (С. Моем Місяць і мідяки). *Сучасні літературознавчі студії*, (11), 342-348.

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day.¹⁰

В этой статье дается краткий обзор антропонимов, их функций статуса, который они получают от этих, и их специфики.¹¹

The article is about the development of the Soviet era of Uzbek educational dictionary. The educational dictionaries created during this period served mainly to teach Russian in national schools.¹²

This article deals with the description of synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language published in different periods, the systematic description of the similarities and differences between the explanations of synonyms in the publications.¹³

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the right of citizens to vote and to be elected, the foundations of the national electoral system, the basis of which are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and ratification by Uzbekistan, constituting the principles of democracy, including independence, legitimacy, transparency and fairness, enshrined and recognized in other international legal instruments.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

¹⁰ NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

¹¹ Орипова, К. (2022). ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4712

¹² Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). HISTORY OF CREATING FIRST BILINGUAL AND REGULATORY EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 147-181.

¹³ Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 117-120.

¹⁴ Tolibjonovich, M. T., & Toxirjonovich, S. D. (2021). The Institutional Mechanisms Of The Development Of The Electoral System In Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(8), 4378-4384.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

We can say next, Ulug Tursunov was one of the first to try to clarify the issues of Uzbek language terminology and wrote works on this topic: "Against the bourgeois aspirations in language terminology", "Issues of Uzbek terminology", "Terminology issues", "Principles of choice of terms in the Uzbek literary language". So, these works reflect on different perspectives and concepts in the field of term formation, collection, arrangement, unification, and publication. It is also worth noting that the confusion in the field of terminology is becoming more and more apparent. For example, the beginning of a concept in different terms and spellings; long explanations instead of clear and concise terms; underutilization of the native language in the creation of the term; One of the sources of enrichment of Uzbek terminology is the fact that there are different approaches to external factors.

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